

MOTHER PROJECT SERIDA Data Management Plan

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The aim of this publication, is to provide a first version of MOTHER'S project data management plan (DMP).

This DMP is a living document that will be revised throughout the project. Two updates are envisaged at M24 (Data Management Plan update 1) and at M48 (Data Management Plan update 2) aiming at revising the data management activities in MOTHER and correcting any procedures, if necessary.

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MOTHER: IMMATURE OOCYTE
CRYOPRESERVATION: EXPLORING INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES FOR GENETIC RESOURCES
PRESERVATION

Oocyte cryopreservation remains at an experimental phase of development, due to the **extremely high sensitivity** of the **oocyte** to low temperatures. Additionally, the number of oocytes that might potentially be cryopreserved or incorporated into an *in vitro* embryo production (IVP), is rather small, which give rise to an undesirable **waste of the Genetic Resources**.

In this context, the aim of MOTHER is to investigate the optimal conditions of **cryopreservation for bovine ovarian cortex tissue (OcT)** to safeguard the **different follicle pools** present in the ovary. In addition, an **innovative *in vitro* culture system will be explored** to retrieve developmental competent oocytes from immature oocytes recovered from ovarian follicles in cryopreserved tissue. The specific objectives are: **(1)** To compare the effects of two OcT cryopreservation protocols: vitrification *versus* (*vs*) slow freezing on oocytes recovered from antral follicles; **(2)** To compare the effects of two OcT cryopreservation protocols: vitrification *vs* slow freezing on preantral follicles within tissue sections; **(3)** To optimize the isolation of preantral follicles from cryopreserved OcT: mechanical *vs* enzymatic methods; **(4)** To establish an efficient follicle *in vitro* culture system (single culture *vs.* sequential culture) for preantral follicles isolated from cryopreserved OcT, and **(5)** To evaluate *in vivo*

the viability of embryos produced from oocytes obtained from both antral and preantral follicles of cryopreserved OoT.

MOTHER, will offer a novel universal technological solution for female fertility preservation with great potential impact on multiple animal species and humans, in different scenarios such as **conservation of animal genetic resources and biodiversity**, management of livestock industry and animal husbandry, world food production and human public health.

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1. Main Info

Title of DMP: **MOTHER PROJECT SERIDA Data Management Plan**

The aim of this Data Management Plan (DMP), is to provide a first version of MOTHER' data management. The DMP is a living document that will be revised throughout the project.

Two updates are envisaged at M24 (Data Management Plan update 1) and at M48 (Data Management Plan update 2) aiming at revising the data management activities in MOTHER and correcting any procedures, if necessary.

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3. License

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1. SUMMARY

MOTHER project Data Management Plan

The aim of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide a first version of data management from different perspectives. This deliverable addresses the management of the steps of all the data's lifecycle:

- MOTHER' datasets: MOTHER expects to generate and collect several datasets. This deliverable describes some needed aspects for dataset identification and description, including naming conventions.
- MOTHER' publications: this document describes the procedure to follow in order to publish scientific content issue from the project.
- MOTHER' data archiving: MOTHER also defines procedures for data archiving and for the sharing of data, both internally, within the consortium and externally. Details about the MOTHER' project repository to be used are included.
- MOTHER' data management guidelines: as a collaborative project in which different partners can need to have access to several kinds of data, a correct management of data security is a priority.
- Legal and ethical aspects regarding data: MOTHER is aware of the legal and ethical implications of a research project, so aspects as the intellectual property rights are also detailed.

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing? Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital? Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it? New data.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

The summary of the data that we'll potentially share is:

1. Numerical, quantitative data defining specific characteristics or values for variables, e.g. data gathered from different experiments with the samples recovered from the slaughterhouse, etc.
2. Qualitative data of specific characteristics (including pictures), e.g. data gathered from different experiments with the samples recovered from the slaughterhouse: morphological characterization of ovarian structures (antral and preantral follicles) and effects of the cryopreservation procedures, breed of the animals of origin.

3. Data derived from analysis or the processing of raw data, such as that obtained from statistical analysis performed during the project.
4. Qualitative data related to project results and/or activities, e.g. management practices, protocols, descriptions of obtained results (articles, abstracts and posters for congresses).

1.1.5 What is its format?

We will choose non-proprietary -open, documented standard, unencrypted- neither full or partial, uncompressed, no embedded files, programs, or scripts without password protection, by using use common character encodings-ASCII, Unicode, UTF-8.

Depending on the characteristics of the data to be shared, we will use:

- Text, Documentation: PDF/A, Plain Text.
- Images/pictures: TIFF, JPEG, PNG, GIF.
- Graphic Image: TIFF, JPEG2000, PNG, GIF.
- Logos (vector formats): Scalable vector graphics
- Video: MOV, MPEG-4.
- Database: XML, CSV.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The data generated in MOTHER will be of a manageable size. Written documents, such as deliverables, should be limited to 15 Mb whenever possible.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information to perform a research work to solve the challenge derived of the lack of an effective, reliable method to preserve the bovine female fertility, in order to contribute to the conservation on the animal genetic resources, and biodiversity.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

MOTHER generated data will have its origin on two sources:

1. Datasets describing the collected samples used for the different experiments
2. Datasets that will have its origin on the project's results and conclusions from the different project's tasks, from the different WPs (from WP1 to WP5), having each WP different types of data.

Initial datasets related to the different WPs will have their origin in the SERIDA and/or in the entity's participant in the project as collaborators.

Datasets issued from the analysis performed by all the MOTHER participant entities will be shared within the consortium in order to be openly shared by using a repository.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry
- Academia

Scientific community, farmers, and fertility clinics would benefit from MOTHER' generated data related to the cryopreservation of ovarian cortex by acquiring a better understanding of cryobiology of the ovarian structures and the possibility of developing new approaches to improve the oocyte long term storage.

1.1.10 Naming the files

A general rule for naming the files will be established:

YEAR/MONTH/DAY_MOTHER_WPX_ENTITY_EXPDATA_Researcher

For example:

20240324_MOTHER_WP2_SERIDA_Ki67 EXP_Researcher.

2. LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Will the described output support any scientific publication? Yes

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication? Yes

2.2 Software

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any software? Yes. Some commercial software will be used to process different types of data:

- Data related with microscopic studies
- Proteomic data
- Extracellular vesicles data

3. FAIR PRACTICES

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset/output?

- Data identifiers: DOI
- Researcher identifiers: ORCID
- Scientific publications: DOI
- Organizations identifiers: ROR
- Projects identifiers: Other

MOTHER will make data findable by using persistent and unique identifiers. Metadata refers to the descriptive data that provides information on other data.

At this early stage of the project, it is difficult to anticipate the specific metadata that will be created during the tasks. Following versions of the DMP will provide a clearer picture regarding this matter. Nevertheless, in order to make MOTHER' data and metadata findable, the following aspects will be taking into consideration:

- Outline data discoverability.
- Outline data identifiability referring to a standard identification mechanism.
- Outline the naming conventions to be used.
- Outline the approach to be used towards search keywords.
- Outline the approach to be used for versioning control.

Following the rules of the funding agency (Agencia Estatal de Investigación), project deliverables and other related documents will be openly available.

- Scientific publications will be published in Open Access venues and in the official repository of the Principado de Asturias (RIA).
- Datasets and any other document issue from MOTHER will be archived in Zenodo.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output? Yes.

Amongst the different types of metadata standards available, the following best practices and guidelines for dealing with Open Data are considered:

- Open Data Foundation, focusing on global metadata standards and the development of open-source solutions promoting the use of statistical data.
- Open Knowledge Foundation, seeking to improve people's access to key information and the ability to use it.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

We will provide descriptive metadata regarding to:

1. Purpose of the generated/collected data, providing a unique dataset identifier
2. Relation to the project's objectives

3. Types and formats of the generated/collected data
4. Origin of the data
5. Dates the data refer to (where applicable)
6. Expected data size (when known)
7. Utility of the data (who will the data be useful to)

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardized vocabularies? Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/es/>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable? Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata? Yes

Key words: Cryobiology, Fertility, Oocyte, Follicle, Ovarian Cortex, Genetic Resources, Biodiversity

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable? Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

ZENODO, <https://zenodo.org/>

ZENODO is a CERN Data Centre-backed research data repository for the long-tail of science, enabling researchers to preserve and share their research output from any science, regardless of the size and format. ZENODO is an innovative and easy to use web-platform, which allows for upload, curation and sharing of the research data through an easy-to-use web interface and integration with other collaboration and data sharing services. ZENODO ensures the discovery and citability of the research output by assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to every upload, as well as promotes software citation and preservation through one-click integration with GitHub.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source? Yes

Zenodo follows repository standards

3.2.1.3 Does the repository/ies assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers? Yes

3.2.1.4 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

ZENODO ensures the discovery and citability of the research output by assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to every upload, as well as promotes software citation and preservation through one-click integration with GitHub.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository support versioning? Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset/output title?

MOTHER PROJECT DATASET

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset/output shared?

Dataset will be openly shared

3.2.2.3 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output? No

3.2.2.4 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee? No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset/output can not be openly shared? Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset/output?
Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available? Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary? Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset/output in the public domain? No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes? Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented? Yes

4.- RESOURCES AND RESPONSABILITY

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

We will use public repositories with no cost for the users.

4.1.2 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Carmen Diez Monforte (orcid: 0000-0001-6909-7814), leader of the project.

5.- ETHICS

5.1 Ethical aspects: There are any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output. The dataset does not contain either sensitive or personal data